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MILESTONE REPORT

TELESCOPES UPGRADED WITH ALPIDE SENSOR

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Abstract:

The EUDET-style beam telescopes enable particle tracking at test beam lines for a large user base. An upgrade with ALPIDE sensors enhances their performance and secures their maintainability for the next decade.

This document reports on the design and performance of two iterations of new ALPIDE-based beam telescope prototypes, where the second is fit for production, which constitutes MS8 in month 45.

AIDAinnova Consortium, 2025

For more information on AIDAinnova, its partners and contributors please see <http://aidainnova.web.cern.ch/>

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Justification for delay:

A prototype of a EUDET-style beam telescope based on ALPIDE pixel sensors has been developed, commissioned, and rolled out to users at the DESY II Test Beam facility. It delivers the expected performance in terms of noise, timing, and rate capability. This confirms that ALPIDE is a sensible choice of pixel sensor for a EUDET-style beam telescopes upgrade.

Problems have occurred, however, in producing additional copies of this system. Significant price increases (as a consequence of the COVID-19 pandemic) of crucial components of the custom hardware would have approximately doubled the cost per telescope. Additionally, it became apparent that the designer of the custom hardware could not guarantee long-term support.

It was decided that these conditions are not acceptable and that an in-house redesign at DESY is the best way to proceed. More control over the design, selection of components with more consideration for long-term availability, full access to all design files, and integration with the Peary software developed for the Caribou DAQ system (WP3.5) will immensely benefit the maintainability of the new system. Working with designers employed by DESY ensures long-term support.

The operation of a single telescope plane has already been accomplished with the new design. A working 6-plane prototype is expected to be ready in September 2023. After this step, the hardware components for all telescope copies should be ordered as soon as possible. It is planned to have them delivered latest in December 2023. The costs of the hardware components per beam telescope are estimated to be approx. 4400 EUR (excluding sensors and mechanics), which represents a significant reduction compared to approx. 9000 EUR for the first design. A first batch of 30 ALPIDE sensors, bonded to chipboards, has already been ordered and is currently ready for shipment from CERN to DESY. Installation of the new telescopes is planned to be carried out when most convenient from the test beam facilities' perspectives.

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Executive summary

The EUDET-style beam telescopes represent an indispensable part of common test beam infrastructure for a large worldwide user base. The upgrade presented in this report ensures their successful operation over at least the next decade.

The ALPIDE pixel sensor replaces the previously used MIMOSA26, improving the telescope performance in terms of tracking efficiency and timing capability.

A first prototype, called Adenium, has been in continuous user operation at the DESY II Test Beam facility since summer 2022 and acts as a proof of concept. It has been very well received by user groups due to its ease of use, stable operation, and improved performance.

Some changes still had to be made to the system to ensure its long-term maintainability. The functionality of the corresponding production prototype was shown in dedicated beam tests at DESY.

1. INTRODUCTION

Beam telescopes provide essential reference measurements for a large fraction of all test beam campaigns. Having them installed as common infrastructure at different test beam facilities allows for overall more efficient beam time usage. The EUDET-style beam telescopes [1], developed in the scope of the first predecessor of AIDAinnova, have been a great success over the last 15 years. Today, seven copies of this system exist around the world. To keep up with the increasing demands in detector development and to ensure maintainability throughout the next decade, their upgrade is pursued within AIDAinnova WP3.

The ALPIDE pixel sensor [2], developed for the current inner tracking system ITS2 of the ALICE experiment, was selected as the most suitable production-grade sensor for the project. A new data acquisition system had to be developed around this sensor, as the previous one is very much tailored around the MIMOSA26 [3] sensor as well as commercial components that have gone out of production. One aspect of the old EUDET-style system that shall be improved upon with the new one is exactly this lack in flexibility and long-term maintainability. In terms of improving the performance, the focus lies on shorter readout times to cope with the increasingly higher particle rates that the detector community is dealing with.

Two iterations of a new ALPIDE-based beam telescope were developed to achieve a version suitable for production. Both are discussed below. A prototype of the first iteration has been in user operation at the DESY II Test Beam facility [4] since summer 2022, has already become the preferred telescope option for most user groups, and represents a proof of concept. The improved second prototype was successfully operated in a beam test and is ready for production.

2. DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS

1.1. GOALS/SPECIFICATIONS

An upgraded version of the EUDET-style beam telescopes should have a similarly small material budget as the current version and be capable of providing a comparable spatial resolution. Furthermore, it should be compatible with existing integrations of user devices. A switch to the new version should require minimum effort from users. This can be assured by integrating the new telescope again with the AIDA2020 trigger logic unit (TLU) [5] and in EUDAQ2 [6]. These are the hardware and software components that give the EUDET-style telescopes their flexibility for integrating additional detectors.

Generally, test beam infrastructure should be robust, easy to use, and stable in operation. Improvements should be made compared to the current version regarding tracking efficiency and timing/rate capability.

During the project, it became clear that maintainability should be one of the main focus points for a new generation of beam telescopes. The corresponding shortcomings of the first prototype were the main driver for the decision to go for a second design iteration.

1.2. ALPIDE

ALPIDE is a production-grade pixel sensor which is well suited to fulfil the above requirements. Besides, it is developed for and currently operated in the ALICE experiment, hence it is readily available and well characterized. The monolithic active pixel sensor (MAPS) can be thinned to 50 μm . It has an active area of ca. 3 cm times 1.5 cm. Its spatial resolution of about 5 μm is slightly worse than that of the MIMOSA26 sensor ($\sim 4 \mu\text{m}$), which results in a slightly worse pointing resolution of a 6-layer telescope ($\gtrsim 3 \mu\text{m}$ compared to $\gtrsim 2 \mu\text{m}$), which is still acceptable.

ALPIDE is operated here in its triggered mode. It reads out all hits that occur within intervals of $O(1 \mu\text{s})$ around the trigger time. The duration of the readout is rate dependent. At the typical beam rates at DESY of about 10 kHz, deadtimes of $\lesssim 10 \mu\text{s}$ should be achievable. This represents a major improvement compared to the 230 μs rolling shutter readout of the current EUDET-style telescopes.

1.3. ADDITIONAL TIMING CAPABILITIES

At rates much larger than 10 kHz, ambiguities of multiple hits per frame can be resolved with one extra tracking layer optimized for time resolution. Such a so-called timing layer can additionally provide precise reference measurements for timing studies. In the scope of MS9 a novel Timepix4-based timing layer has already been developed. Deliverable D3.3 aims to combine it with the new ALPIDE-based telescope.

3. ADENIUM – THE FIRST PROTOTYPE

1.4. DESIGN

Adenium [7] is designed such that each of the six layers can be operated autonomously when connected to a AIDA2020 TLU and a PC via TCP/IP. The latter just needs to have the Adenium software libraries (open source) and EUDAQ2 installed. The full telescope system does not include any additional central hardware components (except a fanout board for the TLU connections).

One telescope layer consists of an ALPIDE sensor, bonded to a chip board as provided by the ALICE collaboration, and a readout board. The central component of the readout board is a system on chip (SoC) (AMD / XILINX Z-7030) whose tasks are:

- Configuring ALPIDE
- Forwarding the TLU clock and triggers, sending back a busy signal
- Interfacing ALPIDE with the EUDAQ2 run control
- Sending hit data from ALPIDE to the PC.

The board has four interfaces:

- 5V power
- Edge connector for chip board
- HDMI (TLU interface)
- TCP/IP (data and slow control)

The support mechanics is mostly taken over from the old EUDET-style telescopes. Only the housings of the individual telescope layers had to be adapted. To synchronize the Adenium data with that of other detectors, it receives the trigger ID from the TLU. Figure 1 shows a photo of a readout board and the layer support mechanics.

Fig. 1: One Adenium layer (without ALPIDE and chip board).

1.5. PERFORMANCE

1.5.1. Pointing resolution

The resolution of the track position interpolated at a DUT, denoted here as pointing resolution, was measured for different beam energies. A seventh Adenium layer was used as DUT. The results are shown in figure 2. As expected, the resolution improves with higher beam energies. The best value at the highest beam energy is $\sim 3 \mu\text{m}$.

1.5.2. Rate capability

Up to beam rates of $\sim 10,000$ particles/s, typical rates at the DESY II Test Beam, Adenium events include on average ~ 1 track. This allows for efficient data taking without an additional timing layer at these rates. Adenium sends a busy signal with a fixed length of $20 \mu\text{s}$. Theoretically, a trigger rate of 500 kHz should therefore be manageable. The actual limit could not be tested at DESY.

Fig. 2: Pointing resolution of Adenium measured for different beam energies at DESY II Test Beam.

1.5.3. Tracking efficiency

The tracking efficiency results from the detection efficiency of ALPIDE, which is well above 99% for optimal configuration [2]. The tracking efficiency for six ALPIDEs all with an efficiency of 99% would be $0.99^6 \approx 94\%$. The efficiencies of the six Adenium layers was estimated in [7] by reconstructing reference tracks based on the respective remaining five layers. The results range between 99.56% and 99.98%, excluding the very last layer for which this method is not adequate.

1.5.4. Ease of use

Adenium has been in user operation at DESY since summer 2022 (see photo in figure 3). It has become the preferred telescope for all groups that tried it so far. It is reported to run for a full week with very few to no crashes. The transition from the MIMOSA26-based telescopes to Adenium works without any issues. The run control via EUDAQ2 works exactly the same. The start-up procedure is, by simply switching on its power, much simpler for Adenium.

Fig. 3: Adenium in user operation at beamline TB22 of the DESY II Test Beam.

1.6. LESSONS LEARNED

Despite Adenium's successful performance, a second iteration was necessary to develop a production prototype for the upgrade of the EUDET-style telescopes. The architecture, which integrates the entire DAQ hardware into a single custom PCB designed around a specific SoC model, does not provide the desired level of maintainability for this project. When the time came for the first production run, some components on the readout board were already not available anymore. This would have required a redesign of the core component of the system already at this early stage. Furthermore, having one SoC per layer, rather than one per telescope, makes this system unnecessarily expensive.

4. THE PRODUCTION PROTOTYPE

1.7. IMPROVED DESIGN

The design changes described here mainly address Adenium's shortcomings in terms of maintainability, especially in the long term. At the same time, they make the system cheaper and, in a sense, more flexible and modular.

The production prototype is based on one central SoC instead of one per layer. In addition, the custom design does not start from the bare SoC. Instead, a commercial system on module (SoM) is used, which consists of a SoC embedded on a small PCB. This decouples and outsources the delicate part of correctly designing the circuitry to connect the chip. The SoM is in turn connected to a commercial base board, which already features a power and an ethernet interface and connects the I/O pins of the FPGA to an FMC interface. This further reduces the custom design effort and adds modularity.

The software and firmware design of this second prototype is realized within the framework of the Caribou DAQ system [8] (see MS11, D3.5) to sensibly exploit an obvious synergy. Accordingly, the same SoM (ME-XU1-15EG-2I-D12E by Enclustra FPGA Solutions) is chosen here as is foreseen for Caribou 2.0.

The remaining hardware components that require custom design are two types of PCBs. One acts simply as a cable adapter to the ALPIDE chip board and is consequently required six times per telescope. The other acts as a hub that interfaces the six telescope layers and the TLU with the SoM via its base board. It is required only once per telescope and connects to the base board directly via its FMC connector. The connection to the individual layers (including power) is realized via DisplayPort cables. Figure 4 shows photos of the system components (left) and the full telescope setup at the DESY II Test Beam (right).

The hardware components that had to be integrated in the Caribou framework include (besides ALPIDE): Clock generators, switcher chips, transceivers, and a custom I2C interface, which are all placed on the hub PCB. Adjustable power supplies are placed on the six ALPIDE adapter boards to be able to compensate for degrading ALPIDE performance over time if necessary.

The telescope runs on the TLU's 40 MHz clock and samples trigger times for robust synchronization with other detectors.

Fig. 4: Components of the production prototype – SoM, base board, hub board, chip board adapter, ALPIDE on chip board (left) and full setup with provisional mechanics at test beam (right).

1.8. BEAM TEST

The performance discussed in the context of Adenium results mostly from that of the ALPIDE sensor, so it does not change for the production prototype. The correct operation of the latter was shown in a beam test at DESY. Figure 5 shows a screenshot of the EUDAQ2 online monitor and validates the EUDAQ2 integration. Furthermore, it was found that the number of telescope events in a run always equals that of TLU events, which shows that the busy logic works reliably. Most importantly, the plots in the screenshot show that, for one trigger event, the hits on the individual layers are correlated, i.e. stem from the same beam particle.

The correct synchronization with another detector was shown by correlating data of the production prototype with that of one synchronously operated Adenium layer. The result is shown in figure 6.

Fig. 5: Screenshot of the EUDAQ2 online monitor showing correlations of column as well as row numbers between the first layer of the production prototype and the remaining five layers.

Fig. 6: Correlations of column (left) and row (right) number between an Adenium layer and layer 1 of the production prototype.

5. REFERENCES

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6. ANNEX: GLOSSARY

Acronym	Definition
TLU	Trigger logic unit
MAPS	Monolithic active pixel sensor
SoC	System on chip
DUT	Device under test
DAQ	Data acquisition
SoM	System on module